

Behavioural Maps for Assisted Navigation

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a new paradigm for robot-assisted navigation: human behaviour is accepted if, at any time, it follows what other humans would do in the same situation. This is achieved through the combination of machine learning and adaptive control. The performed experiments validate the feasibility of this idea.

Index Terms—shared control, assistive robotics, human-robot interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

In assistive robotics, the robot has to provide support to humans, helping them in various types of activities and adapting to their needs. The system has to leave, as much as possible, the person in control of the guidance and intervene only when strictly necessary. This specific paradigm is usually called *shared authority control*, where the robot is jointly controlled by the human and the autonomous system. Previous works on this paradigm are usually more robot-centric: the tasks are described by specific trajectories and rules that force the human to behave as planned, with little to no freedom.

With this work we give more freedom to the human, intervening only when the human behaves noticeably different from what other humans would do in the same situation. We have built a framework using machine learning to classify the features of the trajectories followed by humans in different situations. The motion plan is translated into a grid map, containing the expected behaviours.

Given the current human motion, the control strategy calculates the likelihood with which it belongs to the expected behaviour in that region. A shared authority hyperparameter shifts toward the robot when this likelihood becomes too low. From the implementation point of view, the walker's differential drive is actuated with a visco-elastic control, which is driven by the classification confidence on the observed features. The paradigm is illustrated in Fig. 1.

II. RELATED WORK

To assist a person during locomotion, we need to follow the same basic motion primitives used by humans to obtain high levels of comfort and acceptance in the user. Those primitives can be well approximated by a unicycle dynamics [1], which naturally generates clothoid curves, also known as Euler spirals.

Different works investigated how to retrieve abstract information about the behaviour of humans from their trajectories. Support Vector Machines (SVM) were used by [2] to classify

Fig. 1. Walker representation and adopted reference frames $\langle W \rangle$ and $\langle R \rangle$. In the example shown, the robot will allow any movement to the left (green curves), while it will perform a corrective action for all the non compliant ones (red curves).

different walking styles and behaviours, including movements such as straight, left-turn, right-turn, U-turn, and not walking. The input samples included the normalised coordinates, the orientation, the velocities, and the bounding boxes of the trajectories over the observation window. With Autoencoders (AEs), the objective is to reconstruct the data while learning lower dimensional representations of it, referred usually as its *latent space* representation. In [3] a convolutional Variational Autoencoder (VAE) was used to train a latent representation of the real-world vehicle trajectories represented as a time series of 2D coordinates. In their evaluations the dimension of the latent space was reduced from 10 to 2, with a clear reduction of the reconstruction ability, but with no significant effect on classification accuracy.

III. SOLUTION OVERVIEW

In this work, we used the *FriWalk* robotic rollator, a navigation and walking support for people with mild cognitive deficits. The overall framework of the proposed solution comprises the following steps:

1. Given p_0 and p_f and the a-priori map of the environment, we synthetically generate a set of trajectories using a motion planning algorithm based on PRM coupled with G2 clothoid splines [4]. Such trajectories will be collision-free and will mimic human-like behaviours. This is defined as the *Bootstrap phase*;
2. The generated trajectories are subdivided into adjacent subsets using a sliding window and each subset is analysed by an autoencoder neural network, which extracts the geometric parameters of the trajectory. Then a second neural network classifies each sector by its features $z_{k,\mathcal{P}}$ of the latent space, which are used to build the *behavioural map*, a grid map of admissible human-like manoeuvres to reach p_f . In Figure 2 some of the synthetic trajectories are shown in magenta

Fig. 2. Synthetic trajectories generated with PRM and clothoids.

in a map of the Department of Engineering and Computer Science of the University of Trento, and the corresponding sub-trajectories that will be fed to the classifier are highlighted with the blue circles;

3. As the human moves along the path, the last portion ΔS is reconstructed from the odometry data and classified by the same neural networks to extract a measure of confidence $\varepsilon(t_k)$, that represents the probability with which the user is following the expected class, used to generate the control action. The control signal is constructed as proportional to the similarity measure of the two paths, which is expressed through the likelihood function, i.e., the *confidence*, $\varepsilon(t_k) = \Pr[z_{k,S}|z_{k,P}]$. The control architecture is built as a visco-elastic torque controller that acts on the front wheels of the robot;

4. The *behavioural map* is updated using the actual paths performed by the human agent. In this continual learning process only the paths in which the robot had the least amount of intervention are used.

We firstly trained the autoencoder using 1800 synthetic paths in a simulated conventional cross-intersection, as to have all the three needed cases: straight, right turn and left turn. Then we substituted the decoder part of the autoencoder with a classifier, composed of a single fully connected layer of 3 neurons using the softmax(-) activation function to retrieve the confidence of classification. The trained networks work well in recognising the three classes, in more depth the rate of true positives for the left turns is 88.4%, for the right turns it is 88.3% while for the straight segments it is 76.8%. This lower accuracy in determining the straight zones is attributable to the presence of small natural deviations in motion when the human travels on a "straight" path. This phenomenon can be acknowledged in Figure 2, where in both the blue circles, which progressively analyse the trajectory, we might have some difficulties in distinguishing the actual difference in class (left turn and straight).

In Figure 3 we show the performance of the control for three different user's behaviours. It is fairly noticeable that the more the human user has an erratic behaviour, with many oscillations, the more the control action increases. Otherwise, if the user moves in a smooth expected path, the robot behaves like a passive system, acting as a support aiding device that do not intervene in the trajectory. Even when the control action

Fig. 3. Experimental evidence of the control action behaviour in case of a user acting (orange lines) purposely against the desired path, (green lines) making slight deviations and (blue lines) be very strict to the planned path (a) and the relative controls (b).

is considerable, the user only perceives a quick suggestion of deviation in the current direction. If the suggestion is indulged, then the control signal returns smoothly to zero, otherwise the control continues to correct the trajectory.

The user experience was evaluated through experiments with 16 healthy adults. The proposed framework was compared to a SOTA visco-elastic controller applied to a fixed predetermined path. All the participants preferred the proposed guidance method as they experienced more freedom, as they were not forced to follow a specific route, particularly during the turns.

IV. FUTURE WORK

The key contribution of this work is using the measure of confidence with which the human is complying to the behaviour other users would have in the same situation as parameter in the amount of intervention of the assistive robot. A possible extension of this work could be removing the need for prior knowledge of the environment, the information about the acceptable behaviours in a specific place could be inferred by adding data about the geometry of the area.

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